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A Facile and Effective Four-Component Synthesis of Benzo[4,5]imidazo[1,2-a]-pyrimidine-3-carboxamides Based on Diketene

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Abstract

A novel and efficient four component reaction involving diketene, primary amines, aromatic aldehydes and 2-amino-benzimidazole in the presence of I₂ in refluxing EtOAc for the synthesis of benzo[4,5]imidazo[1,2-a]-pyrimidine-3-carboxamides is reported. Good yields, mild reaction conditions and facile isolation of products in pure forms are advantageous of this methodology.

Keywords: Aminobenzimidazole, benzo[4,5]imidazo[1,2-a]-pyrimidine-3-carboxamides, diketene, iodine-catalyzed reaction, MCR